

Final brochure

June 2025

score

Smart control of the climate resilience

in European coastal cities

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534.

SCORE in a nutshell

The SCORE Horizon2020 project is a four-year EU-funded project aimed at strengthening climate resilience in European coastal cities and regions.

In response to the growing threats posed by climate change, such as extreme weather events, coastal erosion, and sea-level rise, SCORE integrates nature-based solutions, digital technologies and living labs to develop effective, scalable, and sustainable climate adaptation strategies.

The project has been establishing and developing a network of 10 coastal communities (called Coastal City Living Labs - CCLLs) to act on climate change. These CCLLs serve as collaborative platforms where local communities, researchers, policymakers, and businesses co-design and implement climate resilience solutions tailored to their specific geographic and socio-economic contexts.

28
partners

12
countries

01.07.21
31.06.25

10M
euros

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SCORE key achievements

The main results of SCORE can be grouped into 3 categories, each one addressing a specific key area of the project:

Climate change and climate adaptation strategies are generally addressed by top-down processes, creating out-of-touch and disconnected solutions. SCORE innovative and problem-oriented climate adaptation solutions are co-designed and co-created with local stakeholders.

Making Solutions Meaningful at a Community Level through Co-Creation & Living Labs

SCORE key activities & results

- Design and implementation of a **novel Coastal City Living Lab Framework** expanding the Living Lab concept to coastal cities to address climate change adaptation and resilience issues.
- A **co-creation toolkit** including a collection of tools for engaging stakeholders in interactive, engaging, and attractive ways.
- Citizen engagement through **citizen science activities and low-cost sensors** for empowering local communities in monitoring climatic variables.
- Engagement with a young public through **Minecraft and Geodesign games** to increase their knowledge of climate challenges and EBA solutions.
- Free **online courses (MOOCs)** for people to discover, explore, and learn more about climate solutions.

[Read all our achievements in detail!](#)

Increasing Data Availability within CCLLs to support better decision-making

To create effective climate mitigation strategies, **high-quality local data is essential**. However, many communities lack sufficient climate and weather data needed to do so. SCORE developed a suite of tools to expand the data pool available to the CCLLs.

SCORE key activities & results

- Production of reliable **climate and sea level projections, data sets and maps** for all CCLLs to evaluate potential Ecosystem Based Approaches and other interventions to support climate resilience (e.g. multi-hazard risk assessment, downscaling analysis tools, urban-scale short-term and long-term models, flooding and coastal erosion methodologies and maps).
- SCORE ICT Platform** as a data management system for the collection and storing of project data to showcase project results to stakeholders, scientists and citizens.
- Low-cost sensors catalogue** to complement high-cost complex instruments used by experts, for empowering local communities to actively participate in data collection, making observations and analyzing information.
- Interactive and participatory mapping platform (Geosurveys)** allowing for local communities and stakeholders to actively participate in urban environmental monitoring by collecting spatially distributed observations, ground-level data, and geotagged media focusing on local concerns.

Green & Technological Tools for Climate Adaptation Strategies

Effective climate adaptation strategies must integrate green approaches with innovative technology.

SCORE developed comprehensive solutions blending Nature-Based Solutions with digital tools to help us visualize and understand our adaptation options.

SCORE key activities & results

≡ An educational catalogue for coastal climate adaptation using Nature-Based Solutions & Ecosystem-based Adaptations to explore green solutions in coastal areas within combined urban and natural contexts ([SCORE EBA catalogue](#)).

≡ Socio-economic assessments of current and potential interventions including implementation sites, using a **Multiple-Criteria Analysis** and **Cost-Benefit Analysis**.

≡ **New financial risk analysis and solution tools** aimed at estimating the risk faced by the coastal cities before and after the implementation of the proposed EBAs and at increasing their financial resilience.

≡ **Digital Twin and Early-Warning support system** providing a virtual environment for the visualisation of different climate change scenarios, contributing to a prompt reaction to risks, better planning of actions and support to decision making in the governance of coastal cities.

Key publications

Project partners published more than 60 scientific publications in indexed journals. Below is a selection of publications, representative of the different research activities implemented during the project lifetime.

Publications related to Co-Creation & Living Labs

- ≡ [Building Climate Resilience in Coastal City Living Labs Using Ecosystem-Based Adaptation: A Systematic Review](#). Sustainability 2022.
- ≡ [Contextualizing and generalizing drivers and barriers of urban livings labs for climate resilience](#). Environmental Policy and Governance 2024.
- ≡ [A New Approach Towards a User-driven Coastal Climate Service to Enhance Climate Resilience in European Cities](#). Sustainability 2024.

Publications related to increasing data availability

- ≡ [High-level characterisation and mapping of key climate-change hazards in European coastal cities](#). Natural Hazards 2024.
- ≡ [Challenges and Opportunities in Calibrating Low-Cost Environmental Sensors](#). Sensors 2024.
- ≡ [A Technique for the Study of the Volume and Textural Parameter Evolution of Marine Coarse Sediments](#). IEEE Journal of Oceanic Engineering 2025.

Publications related to Green and technological tools

- ≡ [Socio-Economic Assessment of Ecosystem-Based and Other Adaptation Strategies in Coastal Areas: A Systematic Review](#). Marine Science and Engineering 2023.
- ≡ [A semi-quantitative multi-hazard risk assessment framework for European coastal urban areas](#). Geomatics, Natural Hazards and Risk 2024.
- ≡ [Multi-Criteria Analysis of Ecosystem-Based Adaptation Strategies for Flood Risk Reduction in Irish, Italian, and Turkish Coastal City Living Labs](#).
- ≡ [Management of climate resilience: exploring the potential of digital twin technology, 3D city modelling, and early warning systems](#). Sensors 2023.

All scientific publications are available in the SCORE community on Zenodo

[Read the publications](#)

Synergies & collaborations with other projects

In order to boost dissemination of project results and maximize impact, synergies were developed with several international initiatives, networks and EU projects working on climate adaptation.

These collaborations included research collaborations, joint participation in events, joint online promotion, and development of joint documents. Some highlights are featured below.

Adapt4Coast cluster

SCORE has joined forces with the CoCliCo, [PROTECT](#), and [REST-COAST](#) projects within the Adapt4Coast Cluster. **These 4 EU-funded projects aim to enhance climate resilience in European coastal areas and cities by using an integrated solution of smart technologies and nature-based solutions.**

The cluster developed several joint materials: [a factsheet](#), [a joint policy brief](#), a poster presented at the third Forum for the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change in Brussels (May 23, 2024), and [a joint webinar](#).

**ADAPT
4
COAST**

Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change

SCORE was featured on the [CORDIS infopack on climate change](#) in June 2024.

SCORE documents and events are regularly featured in the European Climate Adaptation Platform [Climate-ADAPT](#). The SCORE EBA catalogue has been included in the [Tools database](#).

SCORE is part of the [Thematic Working Group on Integrating Adaptation and Mitigation](#) which has been established as a joint effort of the Mission Implementation Platform ([MIP4Adapt](#)) and the [MAIA project](#). It involves representatives from 12 EU projects dealing with integrative research, policy, and governance approaches to synchronise adaptation, mitigation, and urban development action.

Policy briefs

SCORE participated in the formulation and development of a set of policy briefs, to assist decision making at the local, national and EU levels. Some of these, relevant at the EU level, have been drafted collaboratively with other EU projects.

Recommendations proposed in these documents were developed for implementation in a wide range of cities facing climate change risks.

When will a 2-meter rise in sea level occur, and how might we adapt?

Joint policy brief developed with CoCliCo and PROTECT, presented at the UN Climate Change Conference (COP27).

Integrated strategies for climate resilience in EU coastal cities

Joint policy brief from the Adapt4Coast cluster - September 2023

Climate Adaptation in European Coastal Cities

Outcome of 1st SCORE International workshop at the OpenLivingLab Days - November 2023

Nature-Based solutions for Resilient Coastal Cities

Outcome of the online workshop "NbS for adapting coastal cities to sea level rise" organised by the [Ocean & Climate Platform](#) in April 2024 including insights of coastal adaptation experts and stakeholders involved in Nature-based Solutions projects around the world, including two SCORE partners.

Other recommendations, also targeting local and regional policymakers, have been drafted by SCORE CLLs in different languages, for more efficient dissemination at the local and regional level.

All policy briefs are available [here](#)

Partners

Some key numbers

www.score-eu-project.eu

18

sensors for environmental monitoring deployed in **117 sites**

130+

activities with sensors involving **5400+ participants**

60+

citizen science activities

182

locations mapped in the SCORE Community Geosurveys with...

...159

data contributions and interactions from local communities

70

EBA identified/prioritized by the CCLLs

481

resources on SCORE ICT Platform (SIP)

1200+

enrollments in MOOCs

14

EBA implemented through the project

[score-eu](https://www.linkedin.com/company/score-eu)

[score_h2020](https://www.instagram.com/score_h2020)

[SCORE H2020 Project](https://www.facebook.com/SCORE.H2020.Project)

[@SCORE_EUproject](https://twitter.com/SCORE_EUproject)

[@SCORE_EUproject](https://www.youtube.com/SCORE_EUproject)

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